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Using the latest data to model wild boar abundance at high spatial resolution

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Abstract

Building on a similar analysis conducted in 2024, we present updated estimates of wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) distribution and abundance in the absence of African Swine Fever (ASF). These estimates draw on the most recent density and occurrence data available for Europe. To calibrate model outputs into density values, we used the latest predictions of relative abundance and local wild boar densities (individuals per km²) considered reliable within the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW), supplemented by recent literature (2015 onwards). This expanded dataset increases the number of ASF-free study sites from 77 to 104. Our findings highlight the value of the observatory approach—using study areas with robust, harmonized density estimates—to generate high quality information for epidemiological assessment. The updated model results remain consistent with earlier outputs.

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Key words: (hunting bag, occurrence model, SDM, species distribution)

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Summary

Accurate estimates of host distribution and population density are essential for assessing the spread of diseases such as African Swine Fever (ASF). Here, we provide updated Europe-wide estimates of wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) distribution and abundance using the latest sighting data compiled from GBIF (including iMammalia records) and compare these results with other modelling outputs.

The occurrence modelling approach accounts for spatial clustering of sightings and variation in reporting effort across Europe. We observe an increase in available occurrence data in eastern Europe, likely influenced by intensified efforts from ENETWILD through iMammalia, MammalWeb, and additional EOW study sites.

These results underscore the value of the observatory network—an expanding set of study areas where harmonized, reliable density estimates—in generating high-quality information for epidemiological assessment. This approach also represents the first application of these methods to produce absolute density estimates at the European scale. Continued refinement of this approach will be possible as more data become available.

We advocate for the ongoing development of coordinated wildlife monitoring across Europe. Harmonized monitoring programs are essential to ensure standardization and consistency in data collection, supporting effective management and risk assessment not only for ASF but also for other wildlife diseases and species.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background and terms of reference as provided by the requestor

This contract/grant was awarded by EFSA to: Università degli Studi di Torino (UNITO). Contract/Grant title: Wildlife and One Health: wildlife ecology, health surveillance and interaction with livestock, human population and environment, contract number: OC/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01.

The report covers the first part of work package 4.1A of specific contract 03 of this framework contract to produce revised modelled wild boar abundance estimations at the finest resolution before ASF introduction. Similar estimates for ruminants and carnivores will be produced in 2026. This report complements updates the 2024 report for occurrence modelling and the report entitled "Perspectives from hunting bags for a continuous gradient of relative abundance of wild boars in Europe", tests explicit modelling approach to better capture gradual variation in wild boar abundance based on harvest data.

1.2 Scope of the report

The European Commission (EC) needs regular updated epidemiological analysis of the ASF evolution, based on the data collected from the Member States affected by ASFV Genotype II.

Predicting risk factors for ASF introduction, spread, and persistence in Europe is essential. This information supports updates to disease prevention, control, and management policies. EFSA has received the mandate from the EC to provide technical and scientific assistance by reviewing, identifying and describing the risk factors involved in the occurrence, spread and persistence of the ASF virus in the wild boar population, with a view to inform risk management and enable the preparation of future risk assessment mandates. The risk factor analysis should include the identification of new scientific evidence on the risk factors involved in the occurrence, spread and maintenance of ASF virus. Among those risk factors, the EC requested to study in detail the influence of wild boar density on ASF epidemiology. Therefore, this work is to update the existing data on wild boar densities following the previous approach in 2024. We produce estimates for wild boar abundance which are then combined with data to provide estimates of density. First, we updated modelled wild boar suitability estimations based on occurrence data to update estimations of wild boar probability of presence, a relevant parameter to be used in further risk analysis together with population density. Secondly, as a basis for the calibration of hunting yield-based model into densities, we used the predictions of hunting yield for wild boar modelled at 2x2 km (by ENETWILD Consortium) and included the latest wild boar densities obtained by camera trapping and REM method in the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW), as well as some reliable values extracted from recent literature (2015 onwards).

2 Data and Methodologies

The EFSA working group (WG) on ASF agreed on using the highest spatial resolution available for all models implemented. Thus, the outputs presented here are at 2X2 km spatial resolution.

2.1 Occurrence model

Modelling was conducted using the same methodology described in (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2024), but with updated data: occurrence records, ASF outbreak records, and density estimates for wild boar in Europe. This approach relates mammal sighting records to habitat and environmental parameters to predict the habitat suitability across Europe and then adjusts these estimates accounting for the density of target species recorded in specific study sites.

2.1.1 Data

Sightings of terrestrial mammal species including wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) were obtained from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) on 30/10/2025 (<https://doi.org/10.15468/dl.7q6ubk>). Records (n = 19,116,998) were filtered to only include unique presences (removing duplicates based on date, location and species), based on human observation with a coordinate uncertainty ≤ 2 km, recorded from 1986 (year after release of the European Mammal Atlas; EMMA <https://www.european-mammals.org/>) to 2025. Spatial extent of sightings was restricted to terrestrial land mass within the continent of Europe. This yielded a dataset consisting of 2,752,820 records in total.

Modelling focussed on wild boar distributions in the absence of African swine fever (ASF). By using data sourced on 20/10/2025 from WAHIS/WOAH, providing the location and date for all positive reported cases of ASF in a wild context (n = 45,748 records), introductions/outbreaks were defined by the earliest report date on a regional basis using the Database of Global Administrative Boundaries (GADM) level 1 description (https://gadm.org/download_world.html). Sightings occurring after the initial introduction date, within affected regions, were excluded from analysis (Figure 1).

Both survey effort (biased reporting) and species range (dispersal limitations/stationarity) were accounted for in the modelling, to contextualise species presences in terms of survey effort. Following established approaches (Phillips and Dudík 2008, Croft and Smith 2019, Coomber et al. 2021), sightings of other mid to large terrestrial mammals were used a suitable proxy to measure survey effort (Figure 2). This Figure indicates the location of all wild boar records from the GBIF download, and the locations where sufficient other mammals were recorded showing survey effort with no wild boar records. Following the earlier report, species range was represented using expert-derived range maps from both IUCN (IUCN 2021) and Map of life (Wilson et al. 2009-2019, Burgin et al. 2020, Mammal Diversity Database 2020), providing a broad-scale outline (~ 100 km accuracy) of long-term occurrences (30 years; Figure 3).

As with previous modelling, performed throughout the ENETWILD project (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2022), the same environmental variables describing climate, land cover/use, topography, and anthropogenic influence were considered when explaining species presence (Table 1). Climatic variables are calculated over the last 10 years or so and therefore represent current climate. To mitigate against issues involving multicollinearity amongst predictor variables, an initial Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis was performed across the full model extent (i.e. Europe) iteratively removing variables until none exceeded a minimum co-correlation threshold (VIF score) of 2 (Naimi et al. 2014).

Figure 1: Map showing date of first ASF introduction, derived from outbreak records sourced from WAHIS/WOAH. Darker colours indicate earlier date of introduction.

Figure 2: Map of wild boar occurrence and survey effort defined by sightings of other “associated” mammal species. Compared to the last report the distribution of sightings for all species has increased, particularly in Eastern Europe where iMammalia has been targeted.

Figure 3: Map showing presence of wild boar (GBIF) in relation to assumed species range for wild boar (combined IUCN & Map of Life). Records are updated for this report, but the species range remains the same.

Table 1: Environmental variables used to model wild boar occurrence.

Code	Variable description	Code	Variable description
BIO1	Annual mean temperature	lc_10	Cropland, rainfed
BIO2	Mean diurnal range (mean monthly max temp - min temp)	lc_11	Herbaceous cover
BIO3	Isothermality (BIO2/BIO7) (x100)	lc_12	Tree or shrub cover
BIO4	Temperature seasonality (SDx100)	lc_20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding
BIO5	Max temperature of warmest month	lc_30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)
BIO6	Min temperature of coldest month	lc_40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)
BIO7	Temperature annual range (BIO5-BIO6)	lc_60	Tree cover, broad-leaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
BIO8	Mean temperature of the Wettest Quarter	lc_61	Tree cover, broad-leaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)
BIO9	Mean temperature of the Driest Quarter	lc_70	Tree cover, needle leaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)
BIO10	Mean temperature of warmest quarter	lc_71	Tree cover, needle leaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)
BIO11	Mean temperature of coldest quarter	lc_80	Tree cover, needle leaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)
BIO12	Annual precipitation	lc_90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needle leaved)
BIO13	Precipitation of wettest month	lc_100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)
BIO14	Precipitation of driest month	lc_110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)
BIO15	Precipitation seasonality (coefficient of variation)	lc_120	Shrubland
BIO16	Precipitation of wettest quarter	lc_122	Deciduous shrubland
BIO17	Precipitation of driest quarter	lc_130	Grassland
BIO18	Precipitation of Warmest Quarter	lc_140	Lichens and mosses
BIO19	Precipitation of Coldest Quarter	lc_150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)
GROW	Length of vegetation growing period	lc_152	Sparse shrub (<15%)
SUNRAD	Sun radiation	lc_153	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)
SNOW	Snow cover	lc_160	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water
HFP	Human Footprint Index	lc_180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water
ALT	Mean altitude	lc_190	Urban areas
		lc_200	Bare areas
		lc_201	Consolidated bare areas
		lc_202	Unconsolidated bare areas
		lc_210	Water bodies
		lc_220	Permanent snow and ice

2.1.2 Model methodology

Modelling was performed using the presence-background Maxent model (Phillips et al. 2004), thereby allowing consideration of biased survey effort when comparing environmental samples from locations where wild boar have been recorded against surveyed locations where they have not, in order to infer presence. Assuming non-detection locations represent true absence, predictions can be assumed to reflect probability of presence rather than just an index of relative suitability. Initial predictions were made based on all occurrence data, excluding records made post-ASF introduction, and sites outside the assumed stable range of wild boar, using a subset of environmental variables. Further testing for environmental multicollinearity was performed, excluding any variables that were significantly co-correlated across training locations. Predictions generated using all occurrence records exhibited bias towards surveyed regions; likely due to clustering/oversampling leading to spatial autocorrelation in occurrence of wild boar, with locations close to wild boar populations more likely to report presence even though these areas are not suitable. To address this, spatial thinning was applied to occurrence data, subsampling locations at random to maintain a minimum spacing (Aiello-Lammens et al. 2015). Thinning distance was determined through iterative testing, increasing separation between presence and background points until training AUC (Area Under the ROC Curve) first peaked. As with the previous application of this methodology as part of SC1 WP4 (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2024), a minimum thinning distance of approximately 60 km was selected (Figure 4), consistent with reported maximum dispersal distances for wild boar (Santini et al. 2013). For simplicity, a deterministic thinning approach was used to fit a single model and generate suitability predictions.

Figure 4: Plot showing model performance measured using training AUC based on randomly subsampled data locations to ensure an increasing minimum spacing. A suitable minimum spacing appeared to occur around 60 km, consistent with the reported maximum dispersal distance for wild boar. This thinning distance agrees with the earlier model.

2.1.3 Estimating density based on habitat suitability

Species distribution model outputs were combined with updated density estimates, provided by the European Observatory of Wildlife (see Table 2), to produce a Pan-European density map for wild boar. For each study site, in which a density estimate was calculated, and for which ASF was considered absent, a corresponding boundary polygon was generated, and said estimate was assigned. The resultant shapefile layer was used to extract the underlying habitat suitability values from the SDM output, from cells contained within the extent of each site polygon. Those cells, for which a corresponding density and suitability value were extracted, were then used for density modelling.

Density modelling was performed using a generalised linear model (GLM), with density provided as a response variable, and suitability provided as a predictor (i.e. density \sim suitability). The GLM was fitted with a gaussian error distribution, to density data that was transformed using an optimal box-cox power transformation (*MASS::boxcox*, version 7.3-58.1; (Venables and Ripley 2002), to correct for non-normality. Density was modelled as a quadratic function of suitability – with suitability specified as both a first order (i.e. suitability) and second order (i.e. suitability²) – to account for a non-linear relationship identified during initial model testing. Once fitted, the model was used to predict wild boar densities across Europe, using the entire SDM dataset as a predictor. Since the output was predicted across all of Europe, this can be considered as a wild boar density estimate for all locations in the absence of ASF, including for countries that currently have a limited distribution of wild boar.

Whilst developing the density model, several approaches, in addition to the current method described above, were considered to address issues relating to sites with greater observed wild boar density estimates and yet were predicted to consist of intermediate-level habitat suitability, on average. Conversely, for most sites where wild boar density was estimated, these estimates were comparably lower, with average suitability varying across the entire spectrum (i.e. ranging from 0 – 1). However, these additional methods, consisting of a quantile generalised additive model (Q-GAM; Figure 5 – blue line) and a monotonic quantile regression model (Figure 5 – orange line), both fitted based on the 50th data quantile (i.e. median), either performed similarly to the current model (Figure 5 – red line), with the Q-GAM producing similar density estimates, or deviated from the patterns observed in the fitted data. Given that the basis of the current model is consistent with that utilised in SC1 WP4 (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2024), it was decided to proceed with the generalised linear modelling approach.

Figure 5. Comparison of model fit for different approaches considered when modelling the relationship between wild boar density (individuals per km²) and mean relative suitability – calculated based on 2 x 2km raster cells extracted from the extent of each survey site. Models that were fitted include the current model – generalised linear model fitted with gaussian error structure and quadratic suitability function (red-line) – a quantile generalised additive model (Q-GAM), fitted to the 50th data quantile (i.e. median; blue-line), and a monotonic quantile regression model (orange-line), again fitted to the 50th data quantile.

Table 2: Wild boar densities obtained in the framework of the European Observatory of Wildlife (EOW), as well as some from recent the literature (2015 onwards as reported in the earlier study).

Country	Study site	ASF presence	Administrative figure	Bioregion	Area(ha)	LON	LAT	Year	Density (ind/km ²)	SE	CV	Method density
Bulgaria	Voden-Iri Hisar	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	8000	26.683	43.665	'22	4.38	1.84	42	REM
Croatia	Senj	0	Hunting ground	Southern	3548	14.916178	45.01248	'22	4.09	2.11		REM
Czech Rep.	The Bohemian Switzerland National Park	0	Protected Area	Eastern	8000	14.381	50.876	'24	3.76	2.09	55.5	REM
Italy	La Mandria	0	Protected Area	Western	1604	7.57	45.158	'24	22.5	6.18	27.5	REM
Italy	CACN1/Val Maira	0	Hunting ground	Western	34851	8.538	45.665	'22	10.09	3.37	33.39	REM
Italy	Alpe di Catenaiia	0	Protected Area	Western	2700	11.9123	43.667367	'24	16.3	3.49	21.4	REM
Portugal	ZCA Santulhão	0	Hunting ground	Southern	2948	-6.641	41.573	'24	3.61	1.52	42.1	REM
Portugal	Castreja	0	Hunting ground	Western	2470	-8.136	42.042	'22	6.39	2.65	41.44	REM
Portugal	Lombada	0	Hunting ground	Southern	21184	-6.606	41.864	'22	2.79	1.12	40.12	REM
Portugal	Murça	0	Hunting ground	Western	6404	-7.434	41.461	'22	2.07	0.77	37.13	REM
Portugal	Castelo Melhor	0	Hunting ground	Southern	3329	-7.081	41.04	'22	1.95	0.74	38.14	REM
Portugal	Cubeira	0	Hunting ground	Southern	1812	-7.219	39.677	'22	6.75	1.46	21.67	REM
Portugal	Arrábida	0	Protected Area	Southern	36283	-9.029	38.518	'22	18.45	6.36	34.46	REM

Portugal	Bicas da Serra	0	Hunting ground	Southern	1129	-7.932	37.199	'22	16.26	6.45	39.65	REM
Portugal	Tolosa	0	Hunting ground	Southern	4695	-7.735	39.41	'22	2.92	0.86	29.55	REM
Spain	Parque Natural Sierra del Carche	0	Protected Area	Southern	5942	-1.164	38.427	'24	2.05	0.63	30.6	REM
Spain	Riofrio	0	Hunting ground	Southern	2500	-4.105	39.105	'22	4.88	1.9	38.93	REM
Spain	Doñana	0	Protected Area	Southern	7000	-6.464	36.959	'24	6.46	2.35	36.4	REM
Spain	Arriola (Araba)	0	Hunting ground	Western	4000	-2.389222	42.940055	'24	8.39	2.12	0.25	REM
Spain	Montgó (Alacant)	0	Protected Area	Southern	2086	0.172210	38.801133	'22	14.47	9.59	66.28	REM
Spain	Cabanes-Torreblanca (Castellón)	0	Protected Area	Southern	850	0.1884	40.1756	'22	41.55	16.13	38.81	REM
Spain	Serra Calderona Natural Park - Porta Coeli (Spain)	0	Protected Area	Southern	2918	-0.322553	38.964662	'24	4.25	1.06	25.0	REM
Turkey	Kartdag Wildlife Reserve	0	Protected Area	Southern	11495	33.341	41.782	'24	12.6	6.82	54.3	REM
Andorra	Vedat de caça de la Vall de Ransol	0	Protected Area	Western	2813	1.6441	42.6036	'24	0.11	0.07	62.1	REM
Belgium	Marche-en-Famenne	0	Protected Area	Western	2500	5.365034	50.252736	'24	14.3	2.84	19.9	REM
Belgium	Game Management UUnit 8	0	Hunting ground	Western	10000	4.694	50.802	'24	4.54	1.66	36.6	REM
France	Marais Noir de Saint-Coulban	0	Protected Area	Western	1500	-1.911492	48.5665	'22	2.61	1.3	49.63	REM
Georgia	Lagodekhi National Park	0	Protected Area	Eastern	24450	46.315	41.876926	'22	1.12	0.50	44.6	REM
Hungary	Gemenc	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	20000	18.873	46.217	'24	3.79	1.12	29.6	REM

Israel	Ramat Hanadiv Nature park	0	Protected Area	Southern	1160	34.926	32.554	'24	14.4	3.98	27.6	REM
Montenegro	Orjen Mountain	0	Hunting ground	Southern	6000	18.551724	42.62	'22	2.65	1.18	44.6	REM
Netherlands	Veluwe	0	Hunting ground	Western	2000	5.7	52.23	'24	4.47	1.96	43.9	REM
Serbia	Studenica	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	11000	20.2631	43.3320	'24	1.71	0.62	36.3	REM
Slovakia	Javorie	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	10000	19.140291	48.534234	'22	4.73	2.18	46	REM
Slovenia	Vrhe Vrabče	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	3950	13.943659	45.777460	'22	7.131	2.49	35	REM
Slovenia	Rižana (Primorsko HMD)	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	3657	13.8540	45.5380	'22	11.12	4.34	39.08	REM
Sweden	Stalbo	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	2500	17.12471	60.01757	'22	2.81	3.23	114.79	REM
Poland	Gora Kalwaria	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	4655	21.428	51.865	'21	7.66	4.63	60.444	REM
Belarus	Naliboki Forest	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	14100	26.597	53.981	'21	7.41	1.84	24.831	REM
Germany	Alt Oerrel	0	Hunting ground	Western	4130	10.201	52.961	'21	3.38	1.19	35.207	REM
Germany	Süsing	0	Hunting ground	Western	2720	10.334	53.089	'21	2.31	0.87	37.662	REM
Czech Rep.	Niva	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	2000	16.851	49.445	'21	17.09	7.42	43.417	REM
Bulgaria	Voden-Iri Hisar	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	8000	26.683	43.665	'21	2.35	0.86	36.596	REM
Bulgaria	Panagyurishte	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	2000	24.42	42.494	'21	2.51	1.67	66.534	REM
Croatia	Biokovo	0	Hunting ground	Southern	20000	17.052	43.328	'21	0.35	0.24	68.571	REM

Croatia	Prolom	0	Hunting ground	Southern	7700	16.099	45.253	'24	23.6	5.77	24.5	REM
North Macedonia	Mrezicko	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	2500	22.095	41.163	'21	37.23	10.74	28.848	REM
Albania	Çajupi Mountain (Gjirokastra region)	0	Protected Area	Southern	24447	20.146	42.046	'21	1.5	0.49	32.667	REM
Turkey	Kartdag Wildlife Reserve	0	Protected Area	Southern	11495	33.341	41.782	'21	5.75	2.4	41.739	REM
Italy	La Mandria	0	Protected Area	Western	1604	7.57	45.158	'21	15.25	2.41	15.803	REM
Italy	15. CACN3	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	73000	8.393	45.665	'21	5.84	2.12	36.301	REM
Spain	Amurrio (Araba)	0	Hunting ground	Western	6000	-2.961	43.049	'21	2.12	0.83	39.151	REM
Spain	Riglos (Huesca)	0	Hunting ground	Western	2500	-0.643	42.365	'21	11.31	4.11	36.34	REM
Spain	Parque Natural Sierra del Carche	0	Protected Area	Southern	2100	-1.151	38.427	'21	4.08	1.63	39.951	REM
Portugal	ZCA Santulhão	0	Hunting ground	Southern	2948	-6.641	41.573	'21	3.071	0.794	25.855	REM
Spain	Navarra Eslava	0	Hunting ground	Southern	3500	-1.493	42.595	'18	2.37	3.55		REM
Spain	Parc natural Serra de Mariola (ZCC Agres)	0	Hunting ground	Southern	2450	-0.499	38.76	'18	5.71	3.12		REM
Spain	Valencia Ciutretonda	0	Hunting ground	Southern	4400	-0.376	38.987	'18	13.99	19.8		REM
Spain	Avila Becedas	0	Hunting ground	Southern	2700	-5.651	40.48	'18	3.24	1.7		REM
Spain	Catalunya Montseny	0	Hunting ground	Southern	1500	2.333	41.744	'18	9.5	8.31		REM
Spain	Asturias Sueve	0	Hunting ground	Southern	1800	-5.229	42.452	'18	5.24	2.19		REM

Spain	Quintos Mora	0	Hunting ground	Southern	6600	-4.111	39.368	'24	9.57	2.20	23.0	REM
Spain	Parc natural de la Serra d'Irta	0	Protected Area	Southern	2690	0.317	40.33	'24	11.8	3.33	28.1	REM
Spain	Parc natural del Desert de les Palmes	0	Protected Area	Southern	3096	0.038	40.089	'24	23.6	5.17	21.9	REM
Spain	Parc natural Serra de Mariola (ZCC Agres)	0	Protected Area	Southern	715	-0.499	38.76	'22	4.87	2.8	58.24	REM
Spain	Parc natural Font Roja (Refugi Fau)	0	Protected Area	Southern	525	-0.54	38.656	'22	5.9	3.07	52.11	REM
Portugal*	Castro Laboreiro and Lamas de Mouro	0	Protected Area	Western	3000	-8.18	41.5	'15-'21	2.59		22	DS-CT
Italy*	Casentino	0	Hunting ground	Western	15400	11.49	43.48	'13-'	14			CMR
Italy*	Alpe della Luna	0	Protected Area	Western	1540	12.166	43.651	'19	3.5	2		Faecal counts
Italy*	Berignone	0	Protected Area	Western	2200	10.95	43.331	'19	12.5	3.6		Faecal counts
Italy*	Maremma National Park	0	Protected Area	Western	8900	11.094	42.644	'19	10.5	1.9		Faecal counts
Italy*	Monte Penna	0	Protected Area	Western	1050	11.69	42.775	'19	17.9	5.4		Faecal counts
Italy*	Monterufoli-Caselli	0	Protected Area	Western	4830	10.783	43.255	'19	10.7	2.3		Faecal counts
Italy*	Sasso di Simoni	0	Protected Area	Western	1640	12.290	43.759	'19	16	5.7		Faecal counts
Italy*	Alta Murgia National Park	0	Protected Area	Southern	66087	16.31	40.89	'19	43			Drive Counts
Italy*	Preserve of Castelporziano	0	Protected Area	Southern	5990	12.404	41.695	'18	42.9			DS
Czech Rep.	Mokrá-Horákov/Velký	0	Protected Area	Eastern	1900	16.729	49.239		11	2		REM

	Hornek Natural Reserve											
Georgia	Lukhuni	0	Protected Area	Eastern	4000	42.781908	43.296050	'24	0.42	0.37	87.9	REM
Georgia	Mtirala National Park	0	Protected Area	Eastern	15806	41.8496	41.6602	'23	0.15	0.086	56.4	REM
Georgia	Machakhela National Park	0	Protected Area	Eastern		41.83	41.48	'23	4.36	1.93	44.3	REM
Armenia	Artavan	1	Protected Area	Eastern	4000	41,8843	46,29542	'24	0.09	5.46	61.1	REM
United Kingdom	Loch Ness	0		Western	3100	-3.6679	54.9651	'24	0.66	0.46	68.7	REM
United Kingdom	Forest of Dean	0		Western	4000	-2.5523	51.799	'24	11.9	2.31	19.4	REM
Slovenia	Oljka	0	Hunting ground	Western	2400	15.0200	46.3500	'24	1.03	0.38	37.3	REM
Slovenia	Strunjan	0	Hunting ground	Western	3300	15.0200	46.3500	'24	3.78	1.22	34.3	REM
Poland	Niepołomice	0	Hunting ground	Eastern	5300	50.038803	20.395973	'24	0.60	0.24	39.0	REM
Portugal	Médio Côa	0	Hunting ground	Southern		-7.1221	41.05	'24	0.49	0.15	31.2	REM
Montenegro	Bjelasica Mountain	0	Protected Area	Southern	5650	19.609865	42.895004	'24	2.21	0.75	34.2	REM
Portugal	ZCM Freguesia de Vimioso	0	Hunting ground	Southern	4911	-6.518671	41.585954	'242	3.34	1.12	33.5	REM
Andorra	Ordino Valley	0	Protected Area	Western	3660	1.52	42.63	'224	3.29	1.12	33.9	REM
Spain	Daimiel	0	Protected Area	Southern	4337	-3,730024	39,129105	'24	6.31	1.77	28.1	REM
Germany	Siebengebirge	0		Western		7.23	50.68	'24	2.75	0.91	33.3	REM
Portugal	Herdade da Coitadinha	0	Hunting ground	Southern	995	-7.039249	38.17426	'24	4.04	0.92	22.7	REM

Portugal	Homem-Pedra	0	Hunting ground	Southern	2019	-6.8952	40.3342	'24	2.77	1.05	37.8	REM
Spain	Rosario	0	Hunting ground	Southern	2000	-4.418222	39.103306	'24	7.95	2.89	36.3	REM
Spain	Riaño	0	Hunting ground	Southern	78995	-5.11623	43.07157	'24	2.83	0.88	31.1	REM
Spain	Leizaran	0	Hunting ground	Western	3493	- 1.9504853	43.15728	'24	2.95	0.68	22.9	REM
Slovakia	Cerova Vrchovina PLA	0	Protected Area	Eastern	10000	20,.1	48.22	'24	6.49	2.47	38.1	REM
Spain	Parc Natural del Montgó	0	Protected Area	Southern	2086	0,781284	38,19628	'24	8.44	1.80	0.21	REM
Spain	Parc Natural El Hondo	0	Protected Area	Southern	994	0,781284	38,196284	'24	7.02	1.64	23.3	REM
Germany	Bavarian Forest NP	0	Protected Area	Eadstern	14235	13.45	48.93	'24	3.24	1.01	31.1	REM
Slovenia	Sinji Vrh	0	Hunting ground	Western	4270	15.1600	45.46000	'24	4.54	1.69	37.2	REM
Spain	Utxesa	0	Protected Area	Southern	1042	0,518223	41,49639	'24	22.7	7.82	34.4	REM
Spain	Solanillos	0	Hunting ground	Southern	2800	-2.21	49.97	'24	4.65	0.69	14.9	REM
Italy	San Rossore	0	Protected area	Southern	11000	10.306813	43.717632	'23	39.4	9.58	24.3	REM

SE standard error; CV coefficient of variation;

*Density values collected from literature

3 Results

3.1 Modelled occurrence of wild boar

A single model output of suitability prediction was produced (Figure 6). This shows that most regions have areas of high and low suitability, but in general higher suitability is seen in southern areas, with greater variability as you move inland. We evaluated our model by exploring the importance of different variables and comparing this with the known characteristics of the species; key land cover variables describing conditions such as shelter (trees and shrubs) and resources (crops and grassland) and climatic variables relating to drought (Table 3). We also assessed the transferability of our model by performing a MESS analysis (Figure 7) which highlighted minimal regions where environmental conditions are not represented by the model training data suggesting predictions were reliable. The training AUC of the final model was 0.89, which is considered high.

Based on suitability predictions, a single model output of wild boar density was produced, with density predicted to vary from 0.08 to 5.88 boar km⁻² (Figure 8 and Figure 9).

Table 3: Maxent variable importance

Variable	Percent contribution	Permutation importance
lc_11	11.52	10.59
BIO19	10.71	4.21
BIO18	9.86	12.17
lc_10	8.11	3.25
GROW	6.93	6.90
lc_130	6.87	12.09
lc_60	5.78	6.15
lc_120	4.92	2.67
HFP	4.68	3.07
lc_30	4.67	5.00
lc_90	4.23	7.67
lc_100	3.66	7.01
lc_40	3.13	1.30
lc_12	2.02	4.51
GPW	2.01	2.42
lc_110	1.91	0.39
ALT	1.90	4.25
lc_180	1.50	1.48
lc_210	1.45	1.88
lc_20	1.04	0.91
WIND	1.02	0.46
BIO15	0.91	0.80
lc_200	0.87	0.45
lc_202	0.27	0.08

Ic_150

0.02

0.00

Figure 6: Map showing predicted relative suitability (probability of presence) for wild boar, derived using the presence-background Maxent model. Darker colours denote higher relative suitability/probability. The outputs presented here are at 2X2 km grid. Note: the extent of environmental predictor variables did not extend to include Moldova. The designations employed and the presentation of material on any maps included in this scientific output do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of the European Food Safety Authority concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries. Any designation of Kosovo is without prejudice to positions on status and is in line with United Nations Security Council Resolution 1244 and the International Court of Justice Opinion on the Kosovo Declaration of Independence.

Figure 7: Map showing the coverage of training data in terms of environmental conditions. Training data is broadly representative of all conditions across Europe suggesting predictions can be assumed reliable. Note: the extent of environmental predictor variables did not extend to include Moldova.

Figure 8: Map showing the predicted potential density of wild boar (individual per km²), estimated based on observed densities recorded across European sites using Random Encounter Modelling (REM), and underlying relative suitability, extracted from the current species distribution modelling output. Density was modelled using a gaussian generalised linear model, with density – transformed using a box-cox power transformation – and suitability provided as a quadratic term. The outputs presented here are at 2X2 km grid. Note: the extent of environmental predictor variables did not extend to include Moldova. The designations employed and the presentation of material on any maps included in this scientific output do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of the European Food Safety Authority concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries. Any designation of Kosovo is without prejudice to positions on status and is in line with United Nations Security Council Resolution 1244 and the International Court of Justice Opinion on the Kosovo Declaration of Independence.

Figure 9: Map showing the predicted density of wild boar (individual per km²), modified to exclude those countries where wild boar populations are not believed to be present. Density was estimated based on observed densities recorded across European sites using Random Encounter Modelling (REM), and underlying relative suitability, extracted from the current species distribution modelling output. Density was modelled using a gaussian generalised linear model, with density – transformed using a box-cox power transformation – and suitability provided as a quadratic term. The outputs presented here are at 2X2 km grid. Note: the extent of environmental predictor variables did not extend to include Moldova. The designations employed and the presentation of material on any maps included in this scientific output do not imply the expression of any opinion whatsoever on the part of the European Food Safety Authority concerning the legal status of any country, territory, city or area or of its authorities, or concerning the delimitation of its frontiers or boundaries. Any designation of Kosovo is without prejudice to positions on status and is in line with United Nations Security Council Resolution 1244 and the International Court of Justice Opinion on the Kosovo Declaration of Independence.

Figure 8 indicates the predicted wild boar density across the whole extent of Europe, whereas Figure 9 is clipped to areas where stable wild boar populations are known, using the same clipping map as used in the report on hunting yield (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2026). Figure 8 therefore indicates the potential for further northward spread of wild boar populations across Scandinavia and to some extent into southern Norway, as well as locations in the British Isles which could support wild boar.

4 Discussion

Here we used the occurrence model to generate a habitat suitability and density map of wild boar across Europe, following the methodology used earlier (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2024), but with updated occurrence and density data. Note that this model can predict outside the current range of wild boar (e.g. northern Scandinavia and the British Isles – see Figure 3). Such predictions indicate that the habitat appears to be suitable and thus we may not have captured the actual reason for the current northern limit of this species (Markov et al. 2022).

Comparing these results with the previous work shows some areas (such as the Mediterranean) with higher suitability, and some (such as Scotland) with lower suitability, but there are no substantial differences (compare Figure 6 here with Figure 7 from (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2024). Interestingly, the MESS analysis demonstrates a small increase in area where the model cannot be used to reliably predict suitability. This includes a greater area of the British Isles and some part of the Alps and Pyrenees, the latter is also in agreement with a more general analysis of European mammal distribution indicating where more data would be helpful (Croft et al. 2025). Previously we only produced density maps based on density calibrated occurrence data for three countries, Italy Latvia and Lithuania (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2024). Here we present a pan-European output similar to Smith et al. (Smith et al. 2025). In this latest analysis the maximum density is lower, but more uniform across the continent.

Comparing these results with earlier work indicates that in general there has been a reduction in the area of the MESS analysis and a more uniform distribution (e.g. (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2021).

A comparison with other models is generally only possible at a gross scale, since this work predicts wild boar density at a fine scale. Some similarities occur between this output and other predictions at a gross level, for example the Alpine areas and Benelux countries having a low density along with areas of northern Portugal, Ukraine and Romania (Pittiglio et al. 2018), comparing their Figure 1 produced with hunting data, with our Figure 9. At a more local level there is evidence of low density of wild boar in southern parts of Russia (Zakharova et al. 2024) They used a regression modelling approach in specific regions north of Ukraine and south-east of Ukraine (their Figure 3), which closely matches our output (Figure 9). A Maxent approach to modelling wild boar in Flanders, Belgium (Rutten et al. 2019) indicated the higher density was in the north-eastern part, and there is a high level of agreement with our output (cf. our Figure 9 and their Figure 3). A long-term prediction of wild boar distribution in Scotland using an Agent Based Model (Lovell et al. 2025), produces a patchy distribution with populations in the south-west and some areas of the highlands, which again agrees with our output (comparing their Figure 8 with our Figure 8). Overall therefore, our model output agrees with the output of other modelling that has been done at a fine scale (but has been spatially restricted), and has a good level of agreement with European model output that has been done at a much lower resolution than here.

Comparing the occurrence model and hunting yield-based model (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2026), there are some similarities with the difficulty of predictions, probably due to the non-stationarity as reported therein. This suggests that what we regard as a similar habitat may not be perceived as such by wild boar. This may be due to environmental factors that we do not measure, or due to human factors that adjust the carrying capacity or connectivity. This may also account for why the models predict reasonable densities in areas where they are not currently extant (e.g. northern Scandinavia). This can be investigated further when analyses are completed for other ungulates and carnivores (ENETWILD reports due in 2026).

These results can be used to investigate risk factors and management strategies relating wild boar density and the spread of ASF, particularly in Spain where the data for the hunting model are available at the finest scale.

5 Conclusions

- Occurrence data were used to create estimated distribution and abundance of wild boar across Europe.
- Despite the updated data, the occurrence output is similar to previous models using same methodology.
- These results, plus those from the hunting yield model will be useful to incorporate wild boar density into risk factor analyses for African Swine Fever at the selected spatial scale. Overall, we advocate for the continuous development of the integrated network of wildlife monitoring across Europe, as an increase in locations with a rigorously measured density will improve the output.
- This demonstrates the added value of the observatory approach (a number of study areas where reliable density values are obtained) to generate novel information of high value for epidemiological assessment.
- Considering the density-calibrated hunting-yield model, these maps compare well in western and mediterranean areas.

Glossary

- ASF: African Swine Fever
- GBIF: The Global Biodiversity Information Facility, which hosts international data on all species recording.
- iMammalia: citizen science smartphone app for recording sightings of mammals across Europe
- IUCN: International Union for Conservation of Nature.
- MammalWeb: A web-based system for recording and classifying camera trap images.
- Maxent: A Maximum Entropy Model used to predict a species distribution, based on presence data.
- REM: Random Encounter Model, A method to estimate species densities based on camera trapping
- WAHIS/WOAH: The World Animal Health Information System which collates disease information within the World Organisation for Animal Health.

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